

Spin–orbit coupling is the key to unraveling intriguing features of the halogen bond involving astatine

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Abstract

The effect of spin–orbit coupling (SOC) on the halogen bond involving astatine has been investigated using state-of-the-art two- and four-component relativistic calculations. Adducts between Cl–X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) and ammonia have been selected to establish a trend on going down the periodic table. The SOC influence has been explored not only on the geometric and energetic features that can be used to characterize the halogen bond strength but also on the three main contributions to it that are the charge transfer, the “ σ -hole” (*i.e.* the localized region with a net positive electrostatic potential at the halogen site) and the “polar flattening” (which is related to the effective shape of the halogen site). A surprisingly large increase of the Cl–At dipole moment, due to the inclusion of SOC, has been worked out using four-component CCSD(T) reference calculations, indicating that this bond is significantly more ionic than one may predict. Due to the SOC effect, which induces a peculiar charge accumulation on the At side in the Cl–At dimer, a weakening of the astatine-mediated halogen bond occurs arising from the (i) reduced amount of charge transfer, (ii) decrease of the polar flattening and (iii) lowering of the short-range Coulomb potential. The analysis of the electronic structure of the Cl–At moiety allows for a rationalization of the SOC effects on all the considered features of the halogen bond, including an unprecedented unsymmetrical charge back-donation from Cl–At to ammonia.

Introduction

Since the discovery of astatine, about 80 years ago,¹ many of its chemical–physical features have remained unrevealed.^{2,3} The rarity of this heavy halogen, whose total natural occurrence has been estimated to be even smaller than 30 grams in the Earth's crust at any given time, the absence of any stable isotopes and its radioactive nature are responsible for its inscrutability.

A promising use of this halogen is in the targeted therapy of cancers because one of its artificial isotopes which can be produced in cyclotrons in amounts close to 10^{-9} grams with a half-life time of 7.2 h, is one of a few α -emitting radioisotopes considered suitable for medical applications.^{4,5} This element, indeed, cannot

be characterized through conventional experimental techniques and a direct identification of astatine compounds is practically unfeasible. Only very recently the first ionization potential of At has been accurately measured by laser ionization spectroscopy.⁶ Nonetheless, this partial understanding of astatine chemistry has allowed the preparation of various molecules of biological interest, and an unexpected and significantly higher reactivity of astatide towards arylodonium salts at the radiotracer scale as compared to other halides has been recently observed.⁷

To shed light on the chemical nature of this heaviest halogen, quantum mechanical calculations appear as fundamental tools. Recent theoretical studies on astatine have been focused on the differences between the interactions mediated by this halogen⁸ and those mediated by other halogens.^{9,10} In particular, the differences from its immediate neighbor, iodine, have been investigated. Surprising results are found when the spin-orbit coupling (SOC) effect is taken into account: the At-mediated interactions become weaker compared to the I-mediated ones and the corresponding bonding distances are elongated.^{11,12} The weakening of the interaction energies in At-containing compounds is estimated to be between 11 and 16% for the halogen bond-type and about 18% for the hydrogen bond-type interactions. These findings contradict the commonly accepted fact that a more polarisable halogen should lead to stronger interactions. Indeed, on the basis of its polarizability, At is expected to be the strongest halogen-bond donor on descending along the halogen group (the polarizability values are 3.7, 14.6, 21.0, 32.9 and 42.0 a.u. for F, Cl, Br, I, and At, respectively).¹³ However, as clearly pointed out by Graton and co-workers in their work,¹² inclusion of the SOC effect reveals that the halogen bond mediated by I₂ with ammonia is stronger than that between At₂ and ammonia. Thus, the assumption about the increasing strength of the halogen bond related to the polarizability values breaks down. Furthermore, in the IAt-mediated halogen bond, the intramolecular competition between At and I as donors is shown, although astatine results in the preferred interaction site (at both the scalar and SOC relativistic levels) and the IAt dimer is found to be a stronger halogen donor (on the At side) with respect to I₂. All these unexpected results point out that neglecting spin-orbit coupling in the calculations may lead to incorrect (or incomplete) results. Extensive evidence for the SOC largely affecting the chemical properties of At-containing compounds can be found in the literature.¹⁴⁻²⁰ In particular, SOC effects have been shown to decrease the electronegativity of At by about 10%,¹⁰ reverse the bond polarization in the HAt compound,²¹ increase the polarizability of At⁻ by about 20%,²² and decrease the interaction energy of At-mediated halogen bonds by 20 to 35%.^{9,23} Very recently, the SOC effect on the effective bond order in the heterodiatomic molecule AtX (X = At-F) series has been investigated, where, intriguingly, the SOC has been found to practically leave the effective bond order unchanged in AtCl and AtF.²⁴

Interestingly, quantum chemical calculations which consider the SOC effect can provide guidelines to predict the existence of exotic species, such as in the case of the trihalogen anion IAtBr⁻.²⁵ This compound has been indicated as “the heaviest possible ternary trihalogen species” and its existence has been demonstrated by an experimental performance driven by calculations. Lately, an *ab initio* investigation on the nature of the halogen bond of multivalent AtX_n-CO (X = F, Cl, Br, I; n = 1, 3, 5) complexes was performed by Zheng and co-workers,²⁶ but unfortunately the SOC effects were not included in the calculations. The most rigorous methods to include SOC in a variational scheme are those based on the four-component Hamiltonian derived from the Dirac equation, which are still far from being used in routine studies for geometrical optimizations since they are computationally demanding. Alternatively, one must resort to the derived two-component relativistic methods that explicitly couple spin and orbital angular momenta.

In this context, where evidence for a strong influence of SOC on the properties of astatine compounds has been provided, particularly within the halogen bond interaction framework, it is of crucial importance to accurately investigate the relativistic spin-orbit effect on the main features characterizing the halogen bond involving astatine.

The halogen bond has received considerable attention in recent years since it is extensively involved in many chemical and enzymatic reactions, with relevant applications in the synthesis of new functional materials in crystal engineering, drugs in medicinal chemistry and organocatalysis. According to the definition given by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC), the halogen bond is a non-covalent weak interaction that “occurs between an electrophilic region, associated with a halogen atom in a molecular entity, and a nucleophilic region in another, or the same, molecular entity”.²⁷ Different interaction components such as electrostatic interaction, size repulsion, dispersion, induction and charge transfer (CT) contribute to the halogen bond. The role of charge transfer in halogen bonding has been the subject of several papers, where different computational approaches have been applied to evaluate this property.^{28–31} Besides CT, two other descriptors are commonly considered to characterize the halogen interaction features: the so-called “ σ -hole” and “polar flattening”.³²

According to the IUPAC definition,²⁷ halogens involved in halogen bonding show a localized region with a positive electrostatic potential, the “ σ -hole”. The interaction, which has an electrostatic origin, indeed occurs between this electron-deficient region in the halogenated compound and an electron-rich site on the acceptor, driving the approach of the donor towards the acceptor. The σ -hole region is located on the outermost portion of the halogen atom X, centered on the R–X bond axis.^{33–39} The magnitude of the σ -hole is strictly related to the strength of the electrostatic interaction energy, and therefore its proper understanding and description are of primary importance to model the halogen bond. The “polar flattening” is related to the “effective” shape of the electron charge distribution of the halogen atom X in the molecular entity R–X.^{33,40–42} Analogously to the σ -hole, the origin of the polar flattening is in the electronic charge distribution or, more precisely, in its distortion (flattening) especially in the outer region of halogen X in the direction of the acceptor when the halogen interaction occurs. The contribution of the polar flattening is expected to affect mainly the anisotropy of the size repulsion term of the interaction.^{43–45} Due to its features, the polar flattening is fundamental to describing the position and strength of the repulsive wall in the halogen bond and thus it is expected to have an impact, for instance, on the bond distances.

The present theoretical investigation, carried out using relativistic first principles calculations, is focused on the influence of relativistic spin-orbit coupling effects on the At-mediated halogen bond. Through application of state-of-the-art computational tools, the SOC effect is explored not only on the “classical” parameters (bonding/interacting distances, bonding energies, dipole moments, *etc.*) that can be used to describe and characterize the halogen bond, but also particularly on the three main contributions to it mentioned above: the charge transfer, the σ -hole and the polar flattening. To this aim, adducts of the type Cl–X \cdots NH₃ (X = Cl, Br, I and At) have been selected, where interaction between the dihalogen fragments, Cl–X, and ammonia, the Lewis base, occurs.

The aim is to establish a trend along the halogen group for all the considered features and analyze how inclusion of the SOC effect would affect it.

The peculiarities of the Cl–At \cdots NH₃ adduct, due to the SOC inclusion (at both relativistic two- and four-component levels of theory), are illustrated in detail on the basis of the obtained results. Charge-displacement (CD) analysis,⁴⁶ also in combination with the Natural Orbitals for Chemical Valence (NOCV)

theory, is applied to quantitatively evaluate the charge transfer contribution to the halogen bond and to acquire information on the astatine bonding, which is essential to shed light on the astatine chemistry, *i.e.* on its reactivity and basic properties.

Methodology

Geometry optimization, dipole moment and electron density calculations in this work have been carried out using DFT as implemented in the Amsterdam Density Functional (ADF) package (2016 version).⁴⁷ The relativistic effects have been included by means of the scalar ZORA (Zeroth Order Regular Approximation)^{48–50} and SOC ZORA^{51,52} Hamiltonians for scalar relativistic and spin–orbit coupling effects, respectively.

The computational protocol consists of all-electron (no-core approximation) ZORA/QZ4P Slater-type basis sets, integration accuracy of quality-type Good and GGA BP86 functional.^{53,54}

This computational setup has been validated in a preliminary benchmark study based on previously reported results.^{11,12} The frozen core approximation, basis set size, integration accuracy and functional type parameters have been tested for assessing the accuracy of bonding energies, equilibrium geometries and charge transfer values in the CD analysis, at both the relativistic scalar and SOC levels of theory. The results are provided in the ESI[†] (Fig. S1–S5 and Tables S1–S13).

For the Cl–At molecule the dipole moment has also been calculated at the four-component relativistic *ab initio* level using the Dirac–Coulomb (DC) Hamiltonian as implemented in the Dirac package.⁵⁵ The Hartree–Fock HF, MP2, CCSD and CCSD(T) results are compared with those of the spin-free Dirac–Coulomb (SFDC) Hamiltonian calculations, using different Dyll’s basis sets of double- and triple-zeta qualities.

Charge-displacement (CD) analysis has been applied to quantify the rearrangement of the electron density that arises from the formation of the adduct starting from the two separated constituting fragments, namely Cl–X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) and NH₃, at both the scalar ZORA and SOC ZORA levels. The CD function is mathematically defined as a partial progressive integration on a suitable *z* axis of the electron density difference [$\Delta\rho(x,y,z')$] between the density of the adduct and the sum of the densities of the non-interacting separated fragments at the positions they have in the adduct geometry.⁴⁶

$$\Delta q(z) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dy \int_{-\infty}^z \Delta\rho(x, y, z') dz' \quad (1)$$

The chosen *z* axis is commonly the bond axis between the fragments.

At each point of the *z* axis the CD function quantifies the exact amount of electron charge that is transferred from one fragment to the other, across a plane perpendicular to the bond axis through the *z* point (defined as Charge Transfer, CT). Therefore, negative values of CT indicate charge flowing from left to right and positive values of CT *vice versa* (*i.e.* from right to left). In the present work the CT is always calculated at the so-called “isodensity boundary”, *i.e.* the point where the electron densities of the non-interacting fragments become equal.⁵⁶ The slope of the CD function all over the adduct space gives indications of regions of charge accumulation (positive slope) or charge depletion (negative slope). This successful tool has been previously used to characterize interactions between noble gases and Au,⁴⁶ adducts with hydrogen- or halogen-bonds,^{57–59} organometallic complexes,^{60–63} and electronic excited states.⁶⁴

CD analysis has also been applied to quantify the rearrangement of the electron density in the Cl–At⋯NH₃ adduct starting from the two Cl–At and NH₃ fragments, at the relativistic four-component Dirac–Kohn–Sham level,⁶⁵ using the BERTHA code,^{66–70} with the computational set-up described in the ESI.† To disentangle the charge donation and back-donation contributions to the Cl–At/NH₃ interaction, the CD function has been decomposed by introducing the Natural Orbitals for Chemical Valence (NOCV) scheme.^{71–73} In the NOCV/CD framework,^{74,75} the charge rearrangement occurring upon bond formation is obtained from the occupied orbitals of the two fragments suitably orthogonalized to each other and renormalized (“promolecule”).

The resulting electron density rearrangement $\Delta\rho'$ can be expressed in terms of NOCV pairs which are defined as the eigenfunctions $\varphi_{\pm k}$ of the so-called “valence operator” of the Nalewajski and Mrozek valence theory,^{76–78} as follows:

$$\Delta\rho' = \sum_k \Delta\rho'_k$$

The NOCVs feature the peculiar property that they can be grouped into pairs of complementary orbitals (φ_k, φ_{-k}) corresponding to eigenvalues with the same absolute value but opposite signs. Generally, only a small subset of these NOCV pairs actually contributes to the overall charge rearrangement $\Delta\rho'$, since a large portion of them have eigenvalues close to zero.⁷⁹ The quantities $\Delta\rho$ and $\Delta\rho'$ slightly differ by the density rearrangement occurring on going from the separate fragments to the promolecule, denoted as $\Delta\rho_{\text{anti}}$. This term essentially removes the orbital overlap between the fragments, shifting the electron density from the interfragment region toward the fragments.⁷⁹ However, analyses of the charge transfer based on $\Delta\rho$ and $\Delta\rho'$ typically lead to very similar results.⁷¹ The relativistic NOCVs are clearly four-component vectors. The NOCV approach has recently been implemented in the BERTHA code,⁷³ and it represents the state-of-the-art technique to include the SOC effect in the bonding analysis.

Energy decomposition analysis (EDA)^{80–82} has also been applied at the scalar ZORA level for a quantitative interpretation of the chemical bond between the Cl–X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) and NH₃ fragments in terms of three major contributions to their interaction energy: the electrostatic interaction (ΔE_{elstat}), the Pauli repulsion (ΔE_{Pauli}), and the total orbital interaction (ΔE_{oi}): $\Delta E_{\text{int}} = \Delta E_{\text{elstat}} + \Delta E_{\text{Pauli}} + \Delta E_{\text{oi}}$.

The bonding energy ΔE between the two fragments is related to ΔE_{int} through the expression: $\Delta E = \Delta E_{\text{int}} + \Delta E_{\text{prep}}$, where ΔE_{prep} corresponds to the amount of energy required to deform the separated fragments from their equilibrium structure to the geometry they acquire in the molecule and, eventually, to excite them to their valence electronic configurations. The results of the EDA applied to the Cl–X⋯NH₃ (X = Cl, Br, I and At) adduct series are reported in the ESI† (Table S14).

Results and discussion

Geometries and bonding energies

The SOC effect on the equilibrium geometry has been investigated in the Cl–X⋯NH₃ (X = Cl, Br, I and At) adduct series. In Table 1 the optimized bond distances, calculated at both the scalar ZORA and SOC ZORA levels, and the amounts of the SOC effect (ΔSO) in all the adducts are reported.

Table 1 Distances (Å) and bonding energies $D E$ (kcal mol⁻¹) between Cl–X and NH₃ in the Cl–X···NH₃ (X = Cl, Br, I and At) adduct series. All the calculations have been done at both the scalar ZORA and SOC ZORA levels. DSO is defined as the difference between the SOC ZORA and scalar ZORA values

Cl–X···NH ₃	Cl–X	X···N		DE
Cl–Cl···NH₃				
Scalar	2.115	2.384	—	8.66
SOC	2.115	2.384	—	8.66
DSO	0.000	0.000		0.00
Cl–Br···NH₃				
Scalar	2.266	2.423	—	12.73
SOC	2.268	2.425	—	12.67
DSO	0.002	0.002		0.06
Cl–I···NH₃				
Scalar	2.436	2.567	—	14.34
SOC	2.443	2.580	—	13.88
DSO	0.007	0.013		0.46
Cl–At···NH₃				
Scalar	2.524	2.615	—	16.95
SOC	2.572	2.689	—	13.96
DSO	0.048	0.074		2.99

From Table 1 it is evident that, taking into account the SOC effects, the bond lengths elongate. The emerging trend is that the ΔSO , which quantifies the effect of SOC inclusion, increases on descending along the halogen group. The SOC effect is, however, relevant only for the distances in Cl–At···NH₃, as expected, for the heaviest halogen. Interestingly, the distance between astatine and nitrogen is more greatly affected by SOC inclusion than that between chlorine and astatine (+0.074 Å and +0.048 Å, respectively). In general, according to these findings, the SOC effect is that of lengthening the bonds involving astatine, with the halogen bond (At···N) being the most influenced.

Table 1 also shows the bonding energies calculated at the scalar ZORA and SOC ZORA levels and the differences, ΔSO , between them in all of the different adducts Cl–X···NH₃ (X = Cl, Br, I and At).

From these values it can be noticed that the SOC effect is that the bonding energy decreases, accordingly with the increase of the bond length. The amount of the reduction of the bonding energy is 2.99 kcal mol⁻¹ (about 21% of the total bonding energy) when astatine is involved, while with iodine, the closest halogen, it is only 0.46 kcal mol⁻¹ (only 3% of the total bonding energy).

Interestingly, on comparing the SOC ZORA bonding energy of Cl–At···NH₃ (–13.96 kcal mol⁻¹) with the scalar ZORA bonding energy calculated for Cl–I···NH₃ (–14.34 kcal mol⁻¹), it is found that the former is lower. Thus, the expectation that the strength of the halogen bond along the Cl–X···NH₃ series should increase upon increasing the X halogen size, which is also supported by the scalar ZORA trend in Table 1, breaks down because of the SOC effect when astatine is involved. These results on geometries and bonding energies

highlight the importance of taking into account the SOC effect with heavier atoms which has also been demonstrated by Galland and co-workers in ref. 12.

The fundamental motivation of this work is to understand the reason why the SOC has such a significant impact on weakening the astatine's ability to give a halogen bond. Note that standard energy decomposition analysis is not very useful here because it is mostly based on scalar Hamiltonians, thus overlooking just the SOC effect. Nonetheless, the results of the EDA of the scalar ZORA interaction energies, carried out on the Cl–X⋯NH₃ (X = Cl, Br, I and At) adducts, are reported in the ESI† (Table S14). The calculated scalar values of the three major contributions to their interaction energy, *i.e.* the electrostatic interaction, the Pauli repulsion and the orbital interaction, could be helpful to predict their variations due to the SOC effect.

Before analyzing in detail the SOC effect on the charge transfer (CT), the σ -hole and the polar flattening, it may be interesting to gain first insight into the electron density rearrangement induced by SOC. Thus, in the following section, we evaluate the SOC effect on the dipole moment in the Cl–X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) series.

Dipole moments

The dipole moment is a property that, in its simplicity, gives unambiguous information about the chemical features concerning the polarity of any compound. Evaluating how this value changes by including the SOC effect is fundamental because it highlights the rearrangement of the electron density due to the SOC effect itself.

In Table 2 the dipole moments calculated at the scalar ZORA and SOC ZORA levels of the Cl–X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) molecules are shown and compared with the available experimental values. Indeed, focusing on the values in the dimers, we can get an indication of how much the halogen bond donor (the X halogen) could act as an electrophile because of the charge separation.

Table 2 Dipole moments m (Debye) and effective atomic charges q (a.u.) at the scalar ZORA and SOC ZORA levels of the Cl–X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) dimers. The experimental dipole moments are from ref. 83. Values q have been obtained for each dimer by dividing the dipole moment by the length of the Cl–X bond (Table 1)

	Cl–Cl	Cl–Br	Cl–I	Cl–At
	m	m	m	m
Scalar	0	0.51	1.08	1.70
SOC	0	0.53	1.23	2.60
Δ SO	0	0.02	0.15	0.90
Exp.		0.519 0.01	1.207 0.3%	
	Cl–Cl	Cl–Br	Cl–I	Cl–At
	q	q	q	q
Scalar	0	0.05	0.10	0.15
SOC	0	0.05	0.11	0.22
Δ SO	0	0.00	0.01	0.07

The increase of the dipole moment value in the Cl–X series correlates with the increasing electrostatic energy contribution calculated for the different adducts (see Table S14 in the ESI†), as expected when the X halogen becomes larger on descending along the halogen group.

However, the SOC effect on the Cl–At dipole moment is dramatic: the value changes from 1.70 Debye (at scalar ZORA) to 2.60 Debye (at SOC ZORA). Although the increase of the dipole moment may be somehow

expected, based on the fact that SOC reduces the atomic At electron affinity, its numerical value (0.90 Debye, corresponding to 39% of its total value) is certainly unexpected. To test the reliability of such a strong SOC effect, the dipole moment for the Cl–At dimer has been calculated by employing the state-of-the-art four-component relativistic methods, including the electronic correlation at the highest level of theory. Thus, we carried out Hartree–Fock (HF), MP2, CCSD and CCSD(T) calculations using the Dirac–Coulomb (DC) Hamiltonian and the spin-free Dirac–Coulomb (SFDC) Hamiltonian with different Dyall's basis sets.⁸⁴ The results are compared in Table 3.

Table 3 Dipole moments m (Debye) calculated at four-component relativistic Hartree–Fock (HF), MP2, CCSD and CCSD(T) levels using the spin-free Dirac–Coulomb (SFDC) Hamiltonian and the Dirac–Coulomb (DC) Hamiltonian (values in parentheses) with different basis sets for the Cl–At dimer. DSO is defined as the difference between the DC and SFDC values

SFDC (DC)	Dyall.vdz m	Dyall.vtz m	DSO	Dyall.vdz m	Dyall.vtz m
HF	2.92 (4.02)	2.675 (3.74)	1.10		1.07
MP2	2.15 (3.03)	2.12 (3.00)	0.88		0.88
CCSD	2.23 (3.16)	2.21 (3.14)	0.93		0.93
CCSD(T)	2.08 (2.96)	2.06 (2.94)	0.88		0.88

A clear outcome emerges from the values in Table 3, highlighting the strong impact of the SOC on the Cl–At dipole moment at each level of theory, with a contribution of 1.1–0.9 Debye which is converged with the basis set quality. Noteworthy, the highest level of theory, based on the Dirac–Coulomb Hamiltonian including the electronic correlation at the CCSD(T) level, gives a SOC effect of 0.88 Debye, which is in excellent agreement with DFT calculations based on the ZORA Hamiltonian.

The conclusion is that the Cl–At dimer is even more polarized than one might expect: the SOC induces a larger charge separation with a net CT in the direction from astatine to chlorine.

Based on the above considerations about the dipole moment, it could be hypothesized that the electrostatic interaction in Cl–At \cdots NH₃ should be increased by including the SOC effect. This claim may be true, but in Cl–At \cdots NH₃ the overall bonding energy is reduced and the bond distances are lengthened by the relativistic SOC effects. Therefore there must be another contribution that compensates for this larger electrostatic interaction: the Pauli repulsion.

The effective charges confirm this picture. They represent the simplest relationship between the dipole moment and the equilibrium internuclear separation in diatomic molecules as they can be expressed as $q = \mu/r$, where q is the effective atomic charge, μ is the dipole moment and r is the bond length. The values of the effective atomic charge acquired in the dimers Cl–X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) are also presented in Table 2.

The effective atomic charge value provides the amount, in atomic units, of the net positive charge in each Cl–X dimer. This value is larger when the X halogen becomes heavier. In the case of Cl–At, the SOC effect is that the effective charge increases, as expected because of the large increase of the dipole moment. However, the Cl–At distance also increases. As a result, a larger charge separation between the two halogens occurs: the Cl–At bond acquires a more ionic character when the SOC effect is considered. The effective atomic charge trend obviously correlates with that found for the dipole moment values and for the Cl–X distances calculated in the Cl–X \cdots NH₃ adduct series.

All the quantities analyzed until this point suggest that the Cl–At covalent bond becomes more polarized, coherently with the smaller electronic affinity of the atomic astatine, arising from the spin–orbit coupling effect.

On the basis of the above considerations about the dipole moment and effective charges, it is clear that the SOC has the net effect of making At in Cl–At more positively charged, so that one may expect it to be also smaller-sized and more electrophilic. We may surmise that both the electrostatic interaction (σ -hole) in Cl–At \cdots NH₃ and CT from the Lewis base to At should be increased by including the SOC effect. This claim clearly contradicts the fact that in Cl–At \cdots NH₃ the overall bonding energy is reduced and the bond distances are lengthened by the relativistic SOC effects.

A very useful insight into the rationalization of the SOC effect comes from a simple comparative analysis of the electron density distribution. The difference between the electron densities calculated at the SOC ZORA and scalar ZORA levels in the Cl–At dimer along the bond axis is visualized in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Electron density rearrangement (isodensity surface $0.0003 \text{ e Bohr}^{-3}$) in the Cl–At due to the SOC effect. The difference is computed between the SOC ZORA and scalar ZORA electron densities. The red surface indicates regions where electrons are depleted, while the blue surface indicates regions where electrons are accumulated.

From Fig. 1 a net charge flow from astatine to chlorine is clearly visible with a charge accumulation on the Cl side and a charge depletion in the bond region and on the At side. It is surprising to note that an unexpected charge accumulation is found on the outer astatine side, along the bond axis, in the direction of nitrogen (the blue isosurface on the right), which is an evident SOC effect. Intuitively, this charge accumulation may have a significant impact on the three different contributions to the halogen bond: the CT (charge transfer evaluated through the CD analysis), the polar flattening and the σ -hole.

To rationalize the collected information, the SOC effect on these three different contributions to the halogen bond will be separately quantified and discussed in the following sections.

Charge transfer (CT)

As mentioned in the Methodology section, charge displacement (CD) analysis is applied to accurately and unambiguously measure the charge transfer (CT) value upon formation of Cl–X \cdots NH₃ adducts from the corresponding Cl–X and NH₃ fragments.

To study the effect of the spin–orbit coupling on the amount of electron charge transferred at the isoboundary (see the Methodology section), the CD curves have been calculated for all the Cl–X \cdots NH₃ adducts (X = Cl, Br, I and At) and are depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 CD curves for the Cl–X···NH₃ (X = Cl, Br, I and At) adducts calculated at the scalar ZORA (black line) and SOC ZORA (red line) levels. Black/red points represent, from left to right, the positions of the Cl, X (X = Cl, Br, I and At), N and H atoms in the scalar (black) and SOC (red) geometries, respectively.

The CD curves for Cl–At···NH₃ at the scalar ZORA and SOC ZORA levels and the corresponding isodensity maps are compared in detail in Fig. S6 in the ESI.[†] The charge transfer (CT) values calculated at both the scalar ZORA and SOC ZORA levels are reported in Table 4.

Table 4 Charge transfer (CT) values (electrons) obtained from the CD analysis at the scalar ZORA and SOC ZORA levels for the Cl–X···NH₃ (X = Cl, Br, I and At) adduct series

	<u>Cl–Cl···NH₃</u>	<u>Cl–Br···NH₃</u>	<u>Cl–I···NH₃</u>	<u>Cl–At···NH₃</u>
	CT(e)	CT(e)	CT(e)	CT(e)
Scalar	0.165	0.174	0.163	0.153
SOC	0.165	0.173	0.160	0.134
DSO	0	–0.001	–0.003	–0.019

The CD curves in Fig. 2 clearly exhibit very similar trends for the charge rearrangement (*i.e.* the electron charge transfers from NH₃ to Cl–X), which hardly change with SOC inclusion (the black and red CD curves overlap almost exactly). Interestingly, a remarkable quantitative trend variation is observed in both the Cl–At and Cl–At···NH₃ interaction regions upon inclusion of the SOC effect (compare the black and red CD curves for Cl–At···NH₃ in Fig. 2 and Fig. S6, ESI[†]). Correspondingly, the CT value in the Cl–At···NH₃ adduct is reduced by the SOC effect, as shown by the values listed in Table 4. The amount of this reduction is –0.019 electrons. This CT difference due to the spin–orbit coupling, although so small, accounts for the calculated reduction of the bonding energy. In ref. 85 a semi-empirical conversion factor of 2.5 eV e^{–1} (*i.e.* 2.5 eV for each electron transferred) has been obtained which allows the translation of the transferred electrons into contributions to the stabilization energy in kcal mol^{–1}. On this basis, a reduction of –0.019 electrons in the CT value results in a reduction of the stabilization energy by about 1 kcal mol^{–1}.

Very interestingly, from the CD curves for Cl–At···NH₃ (Fig. 2 and Fig. S6, ESI†), a clear variation of the charge rearrangement on the Cl–At fragment side upon inclusion of SOC (red CD curves) is observed, consistent with the SOC effect on the dipole moment, suggesting that the bond between these two halogen atoms becomes more ionic, which is a peculiarity of the astatine element.

The decrease of the charge transfer (and thus of its contribution to the stabilization energy) in the halogen bond with ammonia (although At is more positively charged) can be rationalized by the unexpected charge accumulation, due to SOC, we found on the outer astatine side, along the bond axis, as we have seen in the previous section (Fig. 1). As suggested by the CD curves for Cl–At···NH₃ in Fig. 2, this SOC effect in the Cl–At bond also extends to the NH₃ bonding.

Before concluding this section, we further analyze the SOC effects on the Cl–At···NH₃ interaction in terms of donor/acceptor properties. To this aim, the CD function has been calculated at the relativistic four-component Dirac–Kohn–Sham level within the NOCV/CD framework,⁷² which allows disentangling the charge donation and back-donation contributions (see the Methodology section).

Although it is known that the bonding with ammonia is mainly dominated by the donation component from its lone pair, Mitoraj and Michalak have recently demonstrated that this ligand can also have a small, but not negligible, contribution as a π acceptor.⁸⁶ The results of our analysis are shown in Fig. 3, where $\Delta\rho$, $\Delta\rho'$ (including their difference, $\Delta\rho_{\text{anti}}$) and the most significant NOCV-pair density decomposition ($\Delta\rho'_k$, $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$) are depicted as isosurface plots together with the corresponding CD functions.

Fig. 3 Bottom panel: CD curves for the Cl–At···NH₃ bond calculated at the relativistic four-component Dirac–Kohn–Sham level. Black points represent, from left to right, the positions of the Cl, At, N and H atoms. Top panel: Isodensity surfaces (0.0014 e Bohr⁻³) for Dr, Dr⁰, and Dr_{anti}, and contributions to Dr⁰ of the four most significant NOCV-pairs (Dr₁⁰, Dr₂⁰, Dr₃⁰, and Dr₄⁰) (isosensity value 0.00015 e Bohr⁻³). Red surfaces indicate charge depletion areas, and blue surfaces indicate charge accumulation areas.

The overall charge rearrangement (represented by either $\Delta\rho'$ or $\Delta\rho$) features a density depletion at the At site towards NH_3 (red lobe) and an electron density accumulation (blue lobe) in the At– NH_3 internuclear region. The electron density accumulation is also in the Cl–At internuclear region (more shifted toward the Cl side) and on the Cl left side (trans to NH_3), which supports the important electron charge rearrangement also occurring within the Cl–At fragment. The CD curves associated with the overall electron density rearrangement (labeled $\Delta\rho$ and $\Delta\rho'$, continuous and dashed black lines, respectively) display similar shapes and trends as observed above for Cl–At \cdots NH_3 in Fig. 2.

The NOCV analysis allows singling out the most important contributions to the total CD curve. The total CD function clearly results mainly from an NH_3 to Cl–At donation component (labeled $\Delta\rho_1'$, red curve in the plot), which is large and positive in the At– NH_3 region, and a component (labeled $\Delta\rho_2'$, green curve in the plot), which is negative and unambiguously identifies the Cl–At to NH_3 back-donation (see the isodensity surface plots shown in the top panel of Fig. 3). Quite surprisingly, only one back-donation component ($\Delta\rho_2'$) significantly contributes to the total CD. The second back-donation component (labeled $\Delta\rho_3'$, light blue curve in the plot) is close to zero all over the adduct region and it is only slightly positive at the NH_3 position. Thus, the CD curves for the $\Delta\rho_2'$ and $\Delta\rho_3'$ related to the two back-donation components are significantly split. The removal of their degeneracy and, very interestingly, the quenching of one of them may be ascribed to the spin–orbit coupling effect, which locally breaks the degeneracy of the 6p At atomic orbitals (the $6p_{1/2}$ and $6p_{3/2}$ spinors differ in both energy and spatial distribution). Finally, we briefly comment on the CD curve corresponding to $\Delta\rho_4'$ (blue curve in the plot). This curve describes an electron density accumulation at the N atom of ammonia, with a positive slope, and it is close to the zero axis elsewhere. This electron density rearrangement seems roughly to balance the $\Delta\rho_{\text{anti}}$ term, which shifts the electron density from the interfragment region toward the fragments as is well shown in Fig. 3. In conclusion, spin–orbit coupling also affects the Cl–At \cdots NH_3 bonding components, by removing the degeneracy of the two Cl–At to NH_3 back-donation components with the surprising quenching of one of them. We will return to this remarkable point in the last section.

At this stage the feature shown in Fig. 1, namely the electron density accumulation on the outer side of At due to spin–orbit coupling, is helpful to introduce and rationalize the SOC effect on the polar flattening and σ -hole contributions to the halogen bond.

Polar flattening

When a halogen atom is covalently bonded, its electron density decreases in its outer region along the extension of the bond and increases in the direction perpendicular to it; the shape of the halogen becomes oblate, with the shorter radius always along the bond. The term “polar flattening” has been introduced to describe this phenomenon. The rearrangement of the electronic density between the Cl and At halogens, which has been visualized in Fig. 1, is entirely due to the SOC effect. Based on this finding, namely an electron charge accumulation on the side of astatine and an electron charge depletion in the region perpendicular to the bond axis, the polar flattening is reduced with respect to that typically observed for the halogen. This electronic spatial distribution (polar flattening) may influence the repulsive barrier.

Furthermore, the negative charge accumulation in the short range (the blue region on the astatine side in Fig. 1) could be responsible for a reduction of the σ -hole (see the next section).

In Fig. 4 we compare the electron density profiles of the Cl–At molecule along the bond axis, one calculated including SOC (SOC ZORA) and the other without (scalar ZORA), with the At nuclei placed at the same position. As one can see, the SOC electron density is always larger than the scalar one. Intuitively, this

situation disfavors a closer approach of ammonia if SOC is taken into account. A quantitative measure of the SOC effect in the polar flattening (shift of the repulsive wall on the At side along the Cl–At bond) may be provided by the Δz value, defined as the difference between two points of the density profiles for the Cl–At molecule (one obtained including SOC and the other without SOC) taking the same density value (see Fig. 4). The Δz value for Cl–At at an isodensity of $0.001 \text{ e Bohr}^{-3}$, representing the molecular surface (this isosurface value is the same as that used typically to map the Coulomb potential in the σ -hole study), is 0.022 \AA . In addition, the SOC effect on the reduction of the polar flattening significantly decreases (smaller values of Δz) for Cl–X with the lighter halogens. For comparison, in the case of Cl–I, we found a value of only 0.004 \AA , and for the remaining systems negligible values (below 0.001 \AA). The electronic density increasing trend matches the increasing size of the X halogen on descending along the adduct series.

Fig. 4 Electron density profiles, ρ (e Bohr^{-3}), along the bond of the Cl–At molecule, calculated at the SOC ZORA (solid line) and scalar ZORA (dotted line) levels. The Δz (\AA) behavior for the Cl–At SOC ZORA (solid line) and scalar ZORA (dotted line) reported as a function of the density value (ρ), see text for details.

The partner interacting with Cl–At in the halogen bond, which in this work is ammonia, while it gets closer to the dimer perceives the Cl–At fragment as enlarged because of such an increase of its electronic density due to the SOC effect. The profile of the electronic density for the Cl–At \cdots NH₃ adduct as a function of the Cl–At/NH₃ distance is depicted in Fig. S7 in the ESI.†

Coulomb potential and σ -hole

The electrostatic is the fundamental contribution to the σ -hole. Thus, the calculation of the Coulomb potential allows the evaluation of the variation of the σ -hole value due to the SOC effect. The molecular surface of Cl–X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) on which the potential is calculated is that with an electron density of $0.001 \text{ e Bohr}^{-3}$. We note that although the choice of this isodensity surface is arbitrary, it is often used for mapping the electrostatic potential.^{87–89} Considering the increased value of the SOC effective charge in Cl–At (see the q values in Table 2), we expect to find a larger contribution due to the σ -hole and a stronger interaction.

The Coulomb potential values at the $0.001 \text{ e Bohr}^{-3}$ isodensity surface of Cl–X, calculated along the z axis (bond axis), are reported in Table 5 for all the Cl–X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) molecules.

Table 5 Coulomb potentials (Hartree e^{-1}) (values in parentheses in kcal mol^{-1}) at the scalar ZORA level for the Cl–X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) series and at the SOC ZORA level for the Cl–I and Cl–At dimmers

	Coulomb potential
Cl–Cl	
Scalar	0.042 (26.4)
Cl–Br	
Scalar	0.057 (35.8)
Cl–I	
Scalar	0.069 (43.3)
SOC	0.069 (43.3)
DSO	–0.0009 (–0.6)
Cl–At	
Scalar	0.085 (53.3)
SOC	0.081 (50.8)
DSO	–0.004 (–2.5)

From the tabulated values a reduction of the Coulomb potential, due to the SOC effect, can be observed. This reduction becomes larger on moving from the iodine molecule to the astatine one. In the Cl–At dimer the SOC effect decreases the Coulomb potential by 0.004 Hartree e^{-1} .

The 3D maps of the Coulomb potential at the 0.001 e Bohr $^{-3}$ isodensity surface at the scalar ZORA level and the SOC ZORA level for the Cl–At molecule are compared in Fig. S8 in the ESI†. The SOC map shows a more emphasized charge separation in terms of Coulomb potential values (more negative values in the chlorine region and more positive values in the astatine region).

The reduction of the Coulomb potential on the isosurface of Cl–At due to the SOC is apparently inconsistent with the larger charge separation between Cl and At due to the spin–orbit coupling effect itself. This discrepancy can be explained through the study of the Coulomb potential as a function of the distance. This is depicted in Fig. S9 in the ESI† for the Cl–At molecule. Enlargements in different spatial ranges are also represented.

In the long range the Coulomb potential calculated including the SOC effect is larger than that calculated at the scalar ZORA level one because of the increase of the dipole moment which is the dominant factor. This effect cannot be seen in the short range: the scalar ZORA potential here is larger than the SOC ZORA one. The enlargements in Fig. S9 in the ESI† (middle and bottom) help in visualizing this effect.

Interestingly, by changing the isodensity surface value, a different value of the Coulomb potential is observed. Considering a smaller isodensity surface, such as 0.005 e Bohr $^{-3}$, the Coulomb potential evaluated on the At side is even more positive than that calculated at 0.001 e Bohr $^{-3}$ isodensity. On the other hand, at a larger isodensity surface value, 0.0001 e Bohr $^{-3}$, the Coulomb potential is smaller than that at 0.001 e Bohr $^{-3}$ isodensity.

Fig. S10 in the ESI† compares the 3D maps of the Coulomb potential (Hartree e^{-1}) at the 0.005 e Bohr $^{-3}$ and 0.0001 e Bohr $^{-3}$ isodensity surfaces of Cl–At with that at the 0.001 e Bohr $^{-3}$ isodensity surface.

The value of the distance at which the two values (scalar and SOC) of the Coulomb potential invert is the one that marks the point in the space, along the bond axis, at which the SOC effect influences the way the ammonia (or any other interacting partner) perceives the σ -hole. Fig. 5 focuses on this inversion region.

Fig. 5 Enlargement of the Coulomb potential (Hartree e^{-1}) plotted as a function of the Cl–At distance (Å) at the scalar ZORA level (black line) and the SOC ZORA level (red line) for the Cl–At molecule. The focus is on the region where the scalar and SOC values invert.

The distance of the inversion is found to be 4.124 atomic units, corresponding to 2.182 Å, which is totally within the region of the halogen bond formed between astatine and nitrogen.

On the basis of these results, a stronger halogen bond would be expected. However, the bonding energies (Table 1) show a significant decrease of the interaction strength, confirmed by the lengthening of the distances in the adduct. Therefore, a counterintuitive SOC effect is found based on the electronic reorganization which is responsible for the reduction of the interaction strength.

In conclusion, all three factors that characterize the halogen bond are affected by the SOC inclusion in such a way that a weakening of the interactions occurs: the reduced amount of charge transfer CT, the reduction of the polar flattening and the lowering of the Coulomb potential in the short range. All these findings are clearly consistent with the SOC effect on the bonding energies (Table 1), which show a significant decrease by 2.99 kcal mol⁻¹ of the interaction strength, confirmed by the lengthening of the distances in the adduct, and on the electronic reorganization on the At side. The density map shown in Fig. 1 essentially visualizes these results.

Rationalization of SOC effects on halogen bonding with astatine

To rationalize the SOC effects on the halogen bond involving At, one needs mainly to understand the two most intriguing features revealed by our analysis: (i) the electron density rearrangement in the Cl–At dimer induced by SOC inclusion and (ii) the quenching of one of the two back-donation contributions to the Cl–At \cdots NH₃ bond. Substantially Fig. 1, which exhibits the peculiar charge accumulation on the outer At side, along the bond axis, in the direction of the incoming Lewis base, and Fig. 3, which shows only one significant back-donation component of the Cl–At \cdots NH₃ bond, must be explained.

One straightforward approach is in terms of the electronic structure of the Cl–At dimer. In Fig. 6 we present the molecular orbital (MO) diagram for Cl–At in the scalar ZORA (left) and SOC ZORA (right) frameworks. Here we will use the scalar ZORA approximation as our starting point; namely, the scalar ZORA Cl–At molecule will be considered as a fragment in the SOC ZORA calculation, and we will discuss how the molecular orbitals are modified by the presence of the spin–orbit interaction.

Fig. 6 Molecular orbital (MO) diagram for Cl–At at the scalar ZORA (left) and SOC ZORA (right) levels of theory.

Upon SOC inclusion, the bonding and antibonding π orbitals (π and π^* on the left-hand side of Fig. 6) will split due to the spin–orbit effect into $m_j = 1/2$ and $m_j = 3/2$ components and a direct correlation between the scalar π , π^* and σ^* MOs and the $48_{1/2}$, $49_{3/2}$, $50_{1/2}$, $51_{3/2}$ and $52_{1/2}$ spinors (right-hand side of Fig. 6) can be obtained. The inclusion of SOC allows the admixture of the $\pi_{1/2}$ -type into the $\sigma_{1/2}$ -type spinors. Moreover, each spinor can be expressed in terms of percentage contributions from the scalar ZORA MOs. In particular, both the $50_{1/2}$ and $48_{1/2}$ spinors have σ^* character (5% and 4%, respectively). Interestingly, both the σ^* and π^* orbitals have more astatine than chlorine character and, in particular, the σ^* orbital is largely localized on the outer At side, along the bond axis. Through the mixing with one component of the occupied $\pi_{1/2}^*$ orbital, the σ^* orbital can be populated, thus explaining the charge accumulation feature on the outer At side in Fig. 1. Notably, this simple framework clearly explains the reason why one of the back-donation components disappears as SOC is taken into account. Indeed, through the admixture with the unoccupied $\sigma_{1/2}^*$ orbital, the same component of the occupied $\pi_{1/2}^*$ orbital can be depopulated, consistent with the quenching of one back-donation component (from Cl–At to NH_3) of the Cl–At/ NH_3 bond observed in Fig. 3.

To get further evidence that the surprising quenching of one of the two back-donation components in the Cl–At \cdots NH_3 bond is a SOC effect and that it is related to the partial occupation of the $\sigma_{1/2}^*$ orbital, NOCV/CD analysis has been performed by increasing the speed of light by 1 order of magnitude ($c = 10 \times 137.036$ a.u.) to approximate the non-relativistic limit and by doubling it ($c = 2 \times 137.036$ a.u.) to partially switch off the relativistic spin–orbit coupling effects.

The results clearly show that the bonding components are significantly modified when relativistic SOC effects are completely switched off (see Fig. S11 and S12 in the ESI[†]). In particular, Fig. 7 summarizes the evolution of the $\Delta\rho_2'$ and $\Delta\rho_3'$ back-donation components from $c = 137.036$ a.u., to $c = 2 \times 137.036$ a.u. and to $c = 10 \times 137.036$ a.u.

Fig. 7 Bottom panel: CD curves corresponding to the Dr_2^0 and Dr_3^0 NOCV back-donation components for the Cl-At \cdots NH $_3$ bond calculated at the relativistic four-component Dirac-Kohn-Sham level with the speed of light c (blue dotted and continuous curves), $2c$ (black dotted and continuous curves), and $10c$ (non-relativistic limit) (green dotted and continuous curves). Black points represent, from left to right, the positions of the Cl, At, N and H atoms. Top panel: Isodensity surfaces ($0.00015 \text{ e Bohr}^{-3}$) for Dr_2^0 and Dr_3^0 and the corresponding NOCV densities ($|j_{+k}|^2$, $|j_{-k}|^2$, $k = 2,3$) (isodensity value $0.003 \text{ e Bohr}^{-3}$) calculated with the speed of light c , $2c$ and $10c$ (non-relativistic limit). Red surfaces indicate charge depletion areas, and blue surfaces indicate charge accumulation areas.

One can clearly see that for $c = 10 \times 137.036$ a.u. (non-relativistic limit, absence of spin-orbit coupling) the $\Delta\rho_2'$ and $\Delta\rho_3'$ back-donation components give identical contributions. On partially switching on the relativistic SOC effects (for $c = 2 \times 137.036$ a.u.) the $\Delta\rho_3'$ component starts to change, and on completely including spin-orbit coupling for $c = 137.036$ a.u. it appears to be very different from $\Delta\rho_2'$, the latter showing the typical back-donation component shape. It is interesting to note that the SOC affects mainly the $|\varphi_{+3}|^2$ (for $c = 2 \times 137.036$ a.u.) and $|\varphi_{-3}|^2$ (for $c = 137.036$ a.u.) NOCV densities (grey surfaces in Fig. 7), leaving the corresponding $|\varphi_{-2}|^2$ and $|\varphi_{+2}|^2$ densities practically unchanged (red surfaces in Fig. 7). Moreover, the σ contribution clearly emerges on including SOC on the Cl side, along the bond (see $|\varphi_{+3}|^2$ for $c = 2 \times 137.036$ a.u. and $|\varphi_{-3}|^2$ for $c = 137.036$ a.u. in Fig. 7), consistent with the electronic structure of Cl-At. Accordingly, the CD curves related to $\Delta\rho_2'$ and $\Delta\rho_3'$ (bottom panel of Fig. 7) display degenerate behavior in the non-relativistic limit (green dotted and continuous curves) and an increasing splitting for $c = 2 \times 137.036$ a.u. (black dotted and continuous curves) which ends up with the quenching of the $\Delta\rho_3'$ component for $c = 137.036$ a.u. (blue dotted and continuous curves). Thus, the electronic structure of Cl-At nicely rationalizes the peculiar SOC effects on the bonding involving astatine.

Conclusion

Comprehension and rationalization of the electronic and bonding properties of the heaviest halogen element, astatine, have been the subject of the present study.

The investigation has been carried out within the halogen-bond interaction framework through exploration of the features of Cl-X \cdots NH₃ (X = Cl, Br, I, At) adducts, such as bond lengths, bonding energies, dipole moments, charge transfer, polar flattening and σ -hole. Since astatine is a heavy element, relativistic effects, particularly the spin-orbit coupling (SOC) effect, have been found to be fundamental to obtaining an accurate description of its electronic and bonding properties. Relativistic scalar ZORA and SOC ZORA and four-component state-of-the-art approaches were applied.

Interestingly, the bonding energy of Cl-At \cdots NH₃ is calculated to be lower than that of Cl-I \cdots NH₃. Thus, the assumption that the strength of the halogen bond increases in the Cl-X \cdots NH₃ series on descending along the X halogen group (based on the increasing halogen polarizability) breaks down because of the electronic features of astatine, which are mainly driven by spin-orbit coupling effects. Consistently, the SOC has also been found to increase the bond distances in Cl-At \cdots NH₃. The surprising increase (up to +0.9 Debye) of the Cl-At dipole moment which has been discovered, due to the inclusion of the spin-orbit coupling effect in the calculations, shows that in the dimer a larger charge separation than that expected on the basis of the scalar calculations occurs.

The results highlight that the Cl-At bond is significantly more ionic than one may predict when the relativistic effects are only included at the scalar level. Therefore, the accurate inclusion of the spin-orbit coupling effect has a significant impact on the nature of the Cl-At bond. The spin-orbit coupling induces a net charge flux from At to Cl in the Cl-At dimer and, on the astatine side, a surprising charge rearrangement takes place, which consists of an electronic charge accumulation along the bond axis in the direction of nitrogen. This peculiar accumulation of electron density is responsible for the reduction of the polar flattening, which measures the deformation of the electron density itself on the astatine side.

The charge-displacement (CD) analysis has been remarkably useful to understand why the charge transfer value from NH₃ to Cl-At decreases, the bonding length (At \cdots N) is elongated and the bonding energy is lowered with respect to the scalar computed corresponding values.

The CD analysis has shown that the inclusion of spin-orbit coupling decreases the net amount of electrons transferred from ammonia to the Cl-At fragment by -0.019 electrons. This reduction is expected to weaken the Cl-At interaction with ammonia by about 1 kcal mol^{-1} .

Surprisingly, within the NOCV/CD framework, which allows disentangling the donation and back-donation contributions to the Cl-At \cdots NH₃ bond, spin-orbit coupling is found to also remove the degeneracy of the two Cl-At to NH₃ back-donation components, and to quench one of them.

By evaluating the Coulomb potential, it has been found how the σ -hole, whose fundamental contribution is the electrostatic one, is influenced by the electronic properties of astatine.

Through the analysis of the Coulomb potential dependence on the distances, it has been discovered that the Coulomb potential, calculated including the spin-orbit coupling, is larger than the scalar potential only in the long range, due to the increased Cl-At dipole moment. In contrast, in the short range, the scalar potential is larger than the spin-orbit coupling one.

In the Cl-At \cdots NH₃ adduct, the weakening of the halogen bond interaction has been elucidated by means of a detailed analysis of the SOC effect on each component of the bond: the reduced amount of charge transfer, the reduction of the polar flattening and the lowering of the Coulomb potential in the short range, all of them arising from the SOC induced accumulation of electron density on the At side in Cl-At. These findings for the astatine adduct demonstrate that, by neglecting the spin-orbit coupling, the description of the halogen bond can be inaccurate or even incorrect.

The Cl-At electronic structure analysis has allowed nicely rationalizing the two most intriguing SOC effects, namely the charge accumulation feature on the outer At side in Cl-At and the quenching of one back-donation component (from Cl-At to NH₃) of the Cl-At/NH₃ bond, through the observed mixing of the $m_j = 1/2$ components of the occupied π^* and unoccupied σ^* orbitals, mainly localized on At.

In conclusion, since each of the contributions to the halogen bond, namely the charge transfer, the polar flattening and the σ -hole, has been separately analyzed, this work may offer a solid theoretical framework to be predictive about the interaction of astatine with different Lewis bases, such as Br⁻ and CO, which are expected to modulate the three contributions to the halogen bond. Of general relevance, the state-of-the-art methodology used in this work, allowing a bond analysis at the relativistic four-component level of theory, coupled with our findings, may contribute to providing novel insight into the rationalization of spin-orbit coupling effects not only on the halogen bond, but also on bonding, reactivity and experimental observables in molecules containing heavy and superheavy elements.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgements

E. R., M. D. S., D. S., L. B. and P. B. gratefully acknowledge financial support from the Ministero dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca (MIUR) and the University of Perugia through the program "Dipartimenti di Eccellenza – 2018-2022" (grant AMIS). This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 764047 of the ESPRESSO project.

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Footnote

1. † Electronic supplementary information (ESI) available. See DOI: [10.1039/c9cp06293a](https://doi.org/10.1039/c9cp06293a)